

FROM CLASSICAL COMPUTATIONAL FRAMEWORK TO AI-ENHANCED LEARNING TOOL FOR SPECIAL MATHEMATICAL FUNCTIONS — DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

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ABSTRACT

The extensive application of special mathematical functions in technical and natural sciences highlights the need for software solutions that will efficiently perform numerical computation of their values. In addition, complexity of this field often presents difficulties in the learning process, motivating the development of our open-source web application called *Special Functions Calculator*.

The initial version of the application was designed to support scientific and engineering applications of special functions. Consequently, functionalities in the initial version provided the numerical computation, along with graphical visualization and basic theoretical background about the selected special function. From an educational perspective, the application lacks the interactive learning support commonly found in modern learning tools. This work presents the design and implementation of an AI-enhanced learning tool for special mathematical functions, extending the existing application with a dialogue system based on an open-source large language model (abbr. LLM), with the aim of providing an interactive and computationally efficient learning experience.

In order to minimize the generation of inaccurate outputs, often referred to as “hallucinations”, a common issue when using LLMs, the model’s training is strictly constrained to data extracted from relevant domain literature using a retrieval-augmented generation (abbr. RAG) framework. By introducing the described learning support, the application evolves from a special functions calculator into a very modern open-source tool capable of supporting learning through explanations and visual interpretation of functions and mathematical expressions. Experimental evaluation shows that system achieves high numerical accuracy in computing values of the special functions, along with 75% correctness, 84.1% faithfulness, and 98.5% relevance in the LLM-based component, which exhibits some limitations in fine-grained function distinguishing and formula rendering.

Keywords: special functions, numerical computation, open-source software, AI-enhanced learning, educational software, large language models (LLM), retrieval-augmented generation (RAG)

1 Introduction

Given the widespread use of special mathematical functions in technical and natural sciences, there is a need for software solutions that will efficiently perform numerical computation of their values [1-5]. Furthermore, the inherent complexity of this field often poses significant challenges in the learning process, which motivated the development of our open-source web application called *Special Functions Calculator*.

The initial version of the application enabled the numerical computation of a selected function for given input parameters, along with graphical visualization and basic theoretical background about the function. These functionalities were designed to support scientific and engineering applications of special functions. However, when the perspective is broadened to the educational domain, the application lacks the interactive support for learning typically found in modern learning tools. This work presents the design and implementation of an AI-enhanced learning tool for special mathematical functions, extending the existing application to provide an interactive and computationally efficient learning experience. To address this, the aim of this work is to enhance the existing application through the integration of a dialogue system based on an open-source large language model (abbr. LLM).

The fields of mathematics and engineering education have long been influenced by technological advancements, consistently introducing innovative tools intended to enhance learning and support complex problem solving [6]. The rapid development and widespread adoption of LLMs have attracted the attention of educators, scholars, and engineering education professionals [7].

Language models have a diverse range of beneficial applications for society, including code and writing auto-completion, grammar assistance, game narrative generation, improving search engine responses, and answering questions [8]. Research has shown that LLMs can achieve impressive performance on very specific and complex mathematical questions after training on domain-specific datasets [9]. Modern LLMs, such as the one integrated into our system, are based on the Transformer architecture, which relies solely on attention mechanisms. This allows for significantly more parallelization, reduced training time, and achieving superior performance in processing complex sequential data [10].

Enhancing classical mathematical learning tools with the use of LLMs is an expected step in the evolution of this kind of tools, but there is a common concern – models sometimes struggle with generation of inaccurate information and often fail to adhere to prescribed output formats, which is particularly problematic for tasks like generating mathematical expressions [11]. “Hallucinations”, as this phenomenon is referred to, constitute a primary limitation of LLMs and they occur due to the model’s reliance on static pre-trained knowledge. A paradigm introduced with the goal of addressing this well-known problem is called Retrieval-Augmented Generation (abbr. RAG). Introducing RAG enables grounding model’s responses in information from a designated knowledge base, which substantially enhances the trustworthiness, accuracy, and relevance of the output [12].

This paper presents an enhanced system for learning special mathematical functions, which integrates an existing classical special functions calculator with LLM, employing a RAG mechanism. Suggested approach enhances the user experience and enables a better and deeper

understanding of these functions by combining numerical computing with a conversational interface capable of providing natural-language answers derived exclusively from relevant domain literature.

2 Baseline application

The initial version of this application, available at <https://github.com/saralazic/special-functions-calculator-web>, has been developed as a numerical calculator for special mathematical functions. In this version, the tool functioned as a classical framework which provided functionalities like:

- Selection of supported special math functions,
- Entry of input values in the form of more complex mathematical expressions, using either a keyboard or a graphical interface,
- Approximation of the value of the special function for given values of the argument and function parameters (e.g. the order of the function),
- Graphical visualization of the selected function,
- Providing basic information about the selected special mathematical function.

Functions which are available for manipulations are some of the most commonly used special functions in engineering and technical sciences, including: Bessel function of the first kind, Gamma and Beta function, some classical orthogonal polynomials including Laguerre and Legendre polynomials, Hermite polynomials (probabilist's and physicist's), Chebyshev polynomials of first and second kind, as well as Jacobi polynomials [13-14].

3 Architecture of the AI-Enhanced System

The system has evolved from a simple monolithic application into a multi-layer architecture which consists of a Graphical User Interface (abbr. GUI, frontend service), a backend service, and a dedicated LLM service. The newly added module called LLM service is composed of a retrieval module and a large language model. Figure 1 illustrates the high-level architecture of the enhanced system: the user interface provides access to features built in an initial version of the tool alongside the new conversational functionality.

Figure 1 High-level architecture of the enhanced system.

Regarding the frontend, GUI has been overall improved in this enhanced version, making the application much more responsive, having a modern design, resolving some minor issues observed in the previous version.

The backend API is responsible for handling everything regarding numerical computation, graphical visualization as well as informational content. Meanwhile, the new dedicated module (LLM service) orchestrates all AI-related operations, including the RAG process, to ensure context-aware and accurate responses. This modular approach improves scalability and allows for independent updates to the computational and conversational components.

4 LLM integration and Retrieval-Augmented Generation

This chapter contains detailed descriptions of design and implementation of the LLM module itself, introduced in the previous section. Special emphasis is placed on the pipeline for retrieval-augmented generation and systematic process of response generation based on relevant domain literature.

4.1 Retrieval-Augmented Generation pipeline

As shown in Figure 1, our LLM service receives user’s questions through the chat interface, orchestrates retrieval of relevant domain knowledge from knowledge bases, and returns a natural-language response.

The RAG concept [15] was introduced to address “hallucinations” problem to which pre-trained neural language models are known to be prone. This limitation occurs partly due to the fact that these models store knowledge implicitly in their parameters, requiring increasingly larger architectures to capture a broader range of facts [16]. To overcome this, retrieval-based approaches utilize external knowledge access to augment language models. Reliability and correctness are highly important in an educational system, therefore RAG paradigm is a particularly suitable when building intelligent chat support in learning environments.

Relevant information is stored in an underlying knowledge base. For every message which user sends in chat, the knowledge base is searched using embedding-based similarity retrieval, and a prompt for Ollama is carefully constructed based on the user’s input, a strict set of rules and information which module retrieved from the base. Figure 2 illustrates the described RAG pipeline.

A critical component of the LLM module is the preparation of knowledge base. As a first step, relevant documents in PDF and LaTeX formats are loaded. Each page is split into chunks of up to certain number of characters, with a 10-15% character overlap in chunks to ensure none of the information is lost at the boundaries. Every chunk is embedded using MiniLM model (sentence-transformers/all-MiniLM-L6-v2) and resulting vectors are inserted into a Facebook AI Similarity Search (FAISS)¹ index. These vectors are associated with their original text and metadata, so they can later be easily retrieved when user makes a request. The FAISS index is then serialized and the

¹ Faiss is a library for efficient similarity search and clustering of dense vectors. It contains algorithms that search in sets of vectors of any size, up to ones that possibly do not fit in RAM. It also contains supporting code for evaluation and parameter tuning [17]. FAISS implementation enables the construction of a high accuracy k-NN graph on 95 million images from the Yfcc100M dataset in 35 minutes, and of a graph connecting 1 billion vectors in less than 12 hours on 4 Maxwell Titan X GPUs, in details described in [18].

document is stored to disk, enabling loading it at runtime without re-processing documents. Notably, LaTeX and PDF documents are stored independently, in two distinct vector stores to maintain data integrity.

Figure 2 An overview of the RAG pipeline.

Every time user sends a message, their input is embedded into a vector using the same MiniLM model which is used in preparations of knowledge bases. FAISS is then used to perform k -nearest neighbors (k -NN) search in order to retrieve the most relevant chunks from each index (in our case it is two chunks from each). The raw text is extracted from retrieved chunks, processed (concatenated all results into one string, formatted) and prompt for Ollama Qwen is constructed using this context. This prompt contains the set of rules and examples, user's input, and the context we just retrieved as described, to generate a grounded response.

4.2 Integration with the LLM model

The integration with LLM model is facilitated through Ollama – an open-source tool designed to facilitate deployment and operations of LLMs [19]. Ollama provides a framework for running open-source LLMs efficiently on local machines, ensuring data privacy and reducing latency [20].

Our dedicated LLM module constructs prompt with RAG as described, and by using Application Programming Interface (API) transmits this prompt and other specific hyperparameters are defined

(e.g. model name, temperature, maximum number of tokens model is allowed to generate) to Ollama [21]. Ollama passes the given prompt to model from a payload and returns generated answer. The model chosen for our implementation is Qwen2.5-7B.

Qwen2.5 has demonstrated top-tier performance on a wide range of benchmarks evaluating language understanding, reasoning, mathematics, coding, etc. Specifically, the open-weight flagship Qwen2.5-72B-Instruct outperforms number of open and proprietary models and demonstrates competitive performance to the state-of-the-art open-weight model which is around 5 times larger. It offers both open-weight from 0.5B to 72B parameters. This model is a significant advancement in LLMs due to enhanced pre-training on 18 trillion tokens and sophisticated post-training techniques, such as fine-tuning and multi-stage reinforcement learning [22].

5 Example of System Usage

Next we will demonstrate how the chat functionality actually can be used.

Suppose a user seeks to know basic information about Chebyshev polynomials of the first kind. They will enter the query: “*What is the Chebyshev polynomial of the first kind? What is the explicit formula for it? Where is the area of practical usage for this polynomial?*”. The frontend will pass the request to the API of the LLM dedicated module. The FastAPI server receives this request, parses the body of the request and initiates the RAG pipeline.

Figure 3 Example of chat usage.

RAG converts exact text of the message into a numerical vector (does embedding) using MiniLM model. Subsequently both FAISS knowledge bases, built from PDF sources and LaTeX sources, are searched in parallel and we get 2 chunks per base. A total of 4 chunks, which contain parts of relevant text about Chebyshev polynomial of the first kind, are then combined into a single string. The final prompt is constructed by concatenating exact text of user’s message, the context RAG just retrieved, and the set of instructions. Instructions include some general guidelines for the model: how to form a response, formatting guidelines, stylistic examples, etc. A payload is then generated

based on this prompt, model, and other parameters chosen for the specific use case (maximum number of tokens, temperature, streaming, settings).

The chosen LLM, Qwen2.5 generates response and returns it back to the system. Response is then parsed, returned to the frontend chat component, which scans text of the response and converts every mathematical equation using KaTeX library into human-readable formulas within the HTML interface.

For this particular case, model returned definition of Chebyshev polynomial of the first kind, including both its recurrence relation and cosine form. It also gave an explanation of what is the most frequent use of this kind of special functions, as illustrated in Figure 3. This is the accurate response, generated based on available context from relevant domain literature.

6 Evaluation

The evaluation of our application consists of two components: calculator evaluation and a chatbot evaluation. The metrics we used for the calculation evaluation are: Mean Absolute Error (deviation, abbr. MAE), Root Mean Square Error (deviation, abbr. RMSE), and relative deviation (error). The MAE measures the average absolute difference between the calculated (predicted) value and actual (reference) value. The RMSE is the square root of the mean of the squared differences between the prediction and the actual observation; this measure assigns greater weight on larger deviations due to the squaring operation. Relative error (deviation) is the ratio of the absolute deviation (error) of a measurement due to the measurement being taken. These metrics are defined as:

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - \hat{y}_i|,$$

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2},$$

$$RelativeError = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{|y_i - \hat{y}_i|}{y_i},$$

Table 1. Metrics for numerical computing of values for implemented special functions

Function	MAE	RMSE	Relative Error
Bessel function of the first kind	2.072093e-15	1.003519e-14	1.414288e-13
The Gamma function	2.871415e-11	1.420581e-10	4.440419e-14
The Beta function	3.642249e-13	1.369852e-12	5.644948e-14
Laguerre polynomial	6.414885e-63	1.709047e-62	3.945446e-62
Legendre polynomial	6.884000e-64	2.170284e-63	4.358762e-63
Jacobi polynomial	1.006301e-81	3.710249e-81	4.868594e-82
Chebyshev polynomial of the first kind	7.512000e-64	1.531227e-63	2.085810e-63
Chebyshev polynomial of the second kind	9.236697e-64	1.603968e-63	4.555872e-63
Hermite physicist's polynomial	1.508560e-60	5.016480e-60	3.280695e-64
Hermite probabilist's polynomial	5.056000e-62	1.577976e-61	1.356095e-63

where y_i is the actual value, \hat{y}_i is the calculated value, and n is the number of instances. Reference value, namely y_i , were obtained using the *mpmath* library in *Python*, which uses 80-digits precision. Values for the Bessel function of the first kind, the Gamma and the Beta function were calculated using built-in high-precision functions directly, while orthogonal polynomials values were generated using three-term recurrence relations in *mpmath*'s arithmetic. These recurrence relations are mathematically exact algorithms, meaning rounding only occurs in the arithmetic itself, which is negligible at 80 digits precision. Consequently, numerical discrepancies primarily reflect floating-point precision limitations rather than algorithmic inaccuracies. Results for every special function provided in the tool are given in the Table 1.

As shown in Table 1, the results indicate high numerical accuracy across all implemented functions. Errors for orthogonal polynomials are extremely small – practically computationally negligible – while slightly higher deviations are observed for the Bessel function of the first kind, as well as the Gamma and Beta functions. Nevertheless, all metrics remain within acceptable bounds, confirming the correctness of the implementation.

The chatbot component was evaluated using the following criteria: correctness of the answer, faithfulness, and relevance. The correctness of the answer is scored as follows: completely correct – 1, partially correct – 0.5, incorrect – 0. The faithfulness of the answer measures whether the answer is grounded in the knowledge base (i.e., whether the RAG mechanism is effectively utilized) and it is scored as: fully – 1, partially – 0.5, hallucinated – 0. Relevance evaluates whether the answer addresses the user's question: completely – 1, partially – 0.5, unrelated – 0. The test set used for evaluation consists of 66 theoretical questions from the domain of special functions (focused on the functions implemented in our application). These questions cover topics such as definitions of these functions, their mathematical expressions, associated differential equations, important recurrence relations, practical applications, weight functions for orthogonal polynomials, and related topics. The results are presented as the ratio of the achieved score to maximum possible score across all answers on questions in the test set.

The system achieved a correctness of 75%, faithfulness of 84.1%, and relevance 98.5%. It was observed that the system struggles to distinguish closely related function variants, such as the variants of the Hermite probabilist's polynomial versus the Hermite physicist's polynomial, as well as the Chebyshev polynomial of the second kind versus that of the first kind. For these cases, the model consistently maps queries for Hermite physicist's polynomial when probabilist's form is requested (although the physicist's variant itself is answered correctly) and similarly confuses Chebyshev polynomial of second kind with that of the first kind. Another noticeable issue is that, for some questions, the system retrieves the correct formula from the context but fails to present it properly, leading to formatting issues or unintended merging of two different expressions into an incorrect form. In such cases, relevance scoring was strictly evaluated: responses that merged formulas were assigned a score of 0.5, even when it was evident that all content was retrieved from the knowledge base but incorrectly rendered.

Additionally, the test set was translated into Serbian language, and the same evaluation was performed in the Serbian setting. For this case, the system shows a significant drop in performance: correctness decreased to 50%, faithfulness to 55.3%, and relevance to 93.9%. In addition to the

issues present in the original test set, the system exhibits further difficulties in context retrieval and domain-specific terminology when operating in the Serbian language. The Qwen model itself exhibits some language-related limitations, including inappropriate translations that incorporate words from other Slavic languages and occasional mixing of Latin and Cyrillic scripts.

Overall, the evaluation results indicate that the proposed system performs reliably in the English setting, with strong numerical precision and high chatbot relevance, while exhibiting notable performance degradation in the Serbian setting. This outcome is completely expected, as many open-source models exhibit substantial degradation with less widely represented, meaning lower-resource languages. A similar phenomenon was recently reported in [24], where a system capable of solving Olympiad-level mathematics problems, despite its overall capability, scored 0% on multiple Mongolian-language problems.

7 Discussion

The implemented intelligent chat module utilizes relevant domain literature in order to enhance the accuracy and relevance of generated answers, as shown, which was the primary objective of this work. Local execution offers advantages such as being able to operate the application offline and data privacy. The synergy between the numerical calculator and an intelligent chat provides significantly higher value than either component individually, giving this tool a decisive advantage over existing platforms that offer either a LLM or standalone numerical computation. Existing online platforms for special mathematical functions are typically limited to calculators for individual functions, or embedded within large general-purpose systems. To our knowledge, currently there is no widely available application that seamlessly integrates numerical computation, structural knowledge bases, and domain-specific conversational AI tailored for this particular mathematical niche.

Existing tools address some of these aspects, but they do not provide a unified solution. Popular general-purpose conversational agents offer natural language interaction. However, they face hallucination-related limitations and are not primarily designed for high-precision numerical calculations. Available RAG-based educational systems are typically developed for broader domains (e.g. mathematics, physics, or STEM in general) and therefore may lack sufficient depth in specialized topics such as special mathematical functions. Additionally, interaction with numerical computation in many of these systems (including even math-focused conversational agents) is predominantly text-based, so the user is required to formulate their request manually, which our system overcomes by providing a GUI specifically designed for numerical evaluation of a wide range of commonly used special functions.

In contrast, mathematical software such as Mathematica/Wolfram Alpha or Symbolab offers highly accurate numerical computation and graphical visualization, which remains their main focus. In newer versions, these tools do also provide natural language interaction, but their main emphasis is still on computation rather than RAG-based explanations tailored to specific topics such as ours. Furthermore, user interaction in these systems is still largely query-driven, so similar to math-focused conversational agents, users are still required to formulate expressions or natural language queries in order to perform numerical evaluation. Therefore, the proposed platform aims to bridge the gap between computational high-precision, domain-specific educational retrieval, and user-friendly numerical interactions.

One of the main limitations of this AI-enhanced learning tool is the fact that it depends on the quality of the knowledge bases used for the RAG pipeline. The selection of documents used to build the knowledge base is a critical step, especially due to the fact that source k -NN search is limited to the k most similar chunks. This means that adding new documents will merely increase the volume of knowledge base, but this is not a guarantee that response quality will improve. The search may fail to retrieve chunks from the most relevant documents as the knowledge base grows excessively large, increasing the risk of “noise” in the retrieved context. To mitigate this issue, reranking techniques could be introduced as an additional step after the initial retrieval. This approach, referred to as Topic-Enhanced Reranking (TER), enables the retrieval system to utilize latent topics within queries and documents, thereby improving the overall precision and semantic relevance of the RAG result [23].

Another challenge is also the fact that it is possible that retrieved context may be incomplete. When knowledge bases are built and text from documents is split into chunks, code tries to split text based on natural units of language (paragraphs, chapters, sections) with a maximum length per chunk. If methods from library used for splitting fails to split the text by natural units, it will default to just number of characters, which is not the perfect scenario when we later retrieve chunks to send context to LLM. It can also happen that k chunks, even if properly split, are just not enough context for LLM to generate perfect response.

The LLM we selected for this implementation has shown advantages for this specific use case over other open source models Ollama provides access to, but it still has certain limitations. During the testing phase, it was observed that formatting sometimes fails, even though the most of the time works as expected. The model currently exhibits limitations in generating responses in Serbian language, even though it is able to respond, translation is not very natural or always correct, occasionally incorporates vocabulary from other Slavic languages or literal translation for some words.

Bearing in mind these limitations, a natural direction of further development of this tool would be to replace the model when new generation open-source models are released. One of the ideas is also to test new models, select those which best fit our needs and provide users an additional option to select which model they want to use. This may be useful to more advanced users who want to experiment with different models and is a common practice in tools which provide LLM support.

The improvement of knowledge base quality is also one of the best ways to improve the accuracy of response. This would be done by carefully reviewing used documents, replacing some less relevant parts of text, limiting the context to only the most relevant text, and adding more LaTeX sources. Another step towards the same goal, among others, is experimenting more with a prompt engineering techniques, forming different instructions, and experimenting with parameters for model. For the case of adding a support for model choice, it would probably be ideal to test which kind of prompts give best results for each model and construct the prompt differently for every model we enable.

Finally, two planned additions to the chat component of the application which would improve user experience chat significantly would be:

- storing a chat history, and

- prompting the LLM in a way that it has available user's previous questions inside a same single session to ensure conversational continuity and contextual coherence.

8 Conclusion

This paper demonstrates the successful transformation of an existing web application – the core of which was a traditional numerical calculator for special mathematical functions – into a very modern, sophisticated AI-enhanced educational platform tailored for upper-level academic students, as well as for specialized researchers. The addition of intelligent chatbot support is provided by integrating an open-source large language model which executes locally. The accuracy and relevance of the model's responses provided by the chatbot are maximized by implementing the retrieval-augmented generation concept. By merging a traditional computational tool with contemporary trends in technology, we achieved to create a comprehensive resource which supports the deep study of special functions as an essential area of mathematics for students in technical sciences, physics, and mathematics. In this sense, the proposed approach illustrates how generative AI can evolve from a passive tool into an active partner in the educational process.

Despite these truly groundbreaking advancements, the tool's performance remains fundamentally constrained by the limitations of the underlying LLM, the efficiency of the retrieval process, and the precision of prompt engineering.

Future work on this, in our opinion, noteworthy and innovative tool will address the aforementioned challenges by making an effort to improve and optimize systematically each stage of this RAG pipeline, as described in detail in the previous chapters. Some of the plans for improving this tool are also: keeping up to date with new and enhanced model configurations (the most crucial), providing user an additional option to choose a model, and fine-tuning system parameters. Additionally, research will focus on prompt optimization and the integration of chat history for improved conversational continuity.

9 Appendix

The knowledge bases utilized in this study are composed of the following sources:

- The LaTeX-based knowledge base is constructed from thesis [12].
- The PDF-based knowledge base includes the relevant chapters from the book [25].

The complete implementation is publicly available on GitHub at:

<https://github.com/saralazic/special-functions-calculator-V2>.

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- Angular – Google LLC
- Ollama – Ollama, Inc.
- Express – OpenJS Foundation

- TypeScript – Microsoft Corporation
- LaTeX – LaTeX Project
- KaTeX – Khan Academy
- Sentence Transformers (all-MiniLM-L6-v2) – UKPLab, Hugging Face
- FAISS – Meta Platforms, Inc.
- Qwen – Alibaba Group
- FastAPI – Sebastián Ramírez
- GitHub – Microsoft Corporation

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